

THE POWER OF THE PEN: AN ANALYSIS ON THE COHERENCE AND COHESION SKILLS OF THE SENIOR HIGH SCHOOL STUDENTS

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ABSTRACT

Effective writing requires both cohesion and coherence to be present in a text, employing various strategies in the writing process, and failure of these means that there is a lack of writing skills. This occurrence is unavoidable and happens often among students. This study analyzed the writing skills, particularly the cohesion and coherence skills of Grade 12 Humanities and Social Sciences students who participated in this quantitative study (n=54) by responding to a survey questionnaire. Results of the survey questionnaire decipher the demographic profile, level of cohesion and coherence skills, and problems encountered by the students in writing. The learners' responses were analyzed and interpreted using descriptive statistical analysis. The findings revealed that Grade 12 students lack the ability to write cohesively and coherently and find difficulties in effectively employing different writing strategies, such as paragraph structuring, vocabulary, and word choice. However, the study found that students excel in using and differentiating the various styles and tones to apply in their written texts. The findings of this study may be used as a basis for classroom policy, highlighting the significance of various written strategies in developing writing skills, particularly in a writing class.

Keywords: *writing skills, cohesion, coherence, written strategies, senior high school*

INTRODUCTION

The emergence of communication as a channel that conveys ideas to ideas plays a significant role in connecting people, culture, and society. Language, on the other hand, is an effective but challenging way of communication. It is used in the day-to-day interaction of people, as it is the key to unlocking a world of knowledge, culture, and understanding. It is the cornerstone of effective self-expression, empowering an individual to convey thoughts, share ideas, and connect with others, making way for personal and professional success. Writing is considered one of the language skills necessary to effectively communicate, along with reading, listening, and speaking skills. Writing is one of the central pillars of language learning that is very important in this era. It allows one to put and exchange their thoughts, information, feelings, ideas, opinions, and knowledge to others in an organized, well-structured piece. Writing represents what we think because the writing process reflects things that are in our minds. Thus, having proper writing skills is also important to meet the learners' academic needs and requirements, helping them express themselves in a meaningful form and adequately tackle the message.

However, despite the importance of writing skills, it remains one of the most challenging and complex skills to learn (Hirvela & Du, 2013). Writing is a complicated skill that requires constant practice and improvement, despite its importance. It is one of the hardest and most difficult abilities to learn since it requires an understanding of language structure, creativity, organization, and successful communication. Most learners find difficulties and are reluctant to write what is on their mind and produce a coherent piece of text due to the lack of required skills at utilizing the structure of language, vocabulary, punctuation, and other sub-skills. In order to form a meaningful, comprehensive, and logical message to convey, a writer must be aware and knowledgeable about the different rules, elements, and strategies in writing (Hyland, 2019).

Learners often struggle to write coherently due to insufficient skills in grammar, vocabulary, punctuation, and organization, which can lead to a lack of confidence and reluctance to express their thoughts in writing. Badi (2015) concludes that the primary challenge encountered in writing is language usage, coherence, and cohesion, following struggles with asserting their unique voices and choosing meaningful topics and appropriate references. This difficulty makes students perceive themselves as less proficient than experienced and intelligent writers, leading to a lack of confidence in contributing their ideas alongside those of more seasoned authors. Essentially, students may doubt their abilities and, as a result, may be reluctant to share their thoughts and feelings. Students lack confidence due to their uncertainty regarding the quality of their work and compare it to their peers, which only results in their discomfort (Bakhtiar, 2023).

Through measuring learners' level of writing skills in English, this study will contribute to the existing literature and provide suggestions and recommendations beneficial to the students and teachers on how they can be aware of their writing skills and be able to implement programs to improve. It is inevitable to have failure in writing; mistakes are normal. The essential part is when people try to improve themselves with the willingness to reach the purpose of communication, which is mutual understanding.

Facing the Pen's mightiest dilemma

Students today lack writing abilities since they rely more on technology and electronics. The development of technology paved the way for rapid or ready-made responses or outcomes of an activity or work (Durga & Rao, 2018). The development of technology, like artificial intelligence, has made some learners' tasks substantially simpler. However, it restricts their opportunities to write quality texts. Technology is the application of scientific knowledge and its interrelation with people, the environment, and society in general (Ansu-Kyeremeh & Goosen, 2022). Through the development of technology, students rely increasingly on artificial intelligence, which causes them to lack understanding of the components of writing that are necessary to create a coherent total.

Poor English grammar and usage, a lack of creative ideas, ineffective teaching methods, insufficient vocabulary, weak sentence structure, inexperienced teachers, inappropriate uses of words, and rhetorical conventions are the reasons for difficulty in writing. A study done by Seyabi & Tuzlukova (2014) shows that a group of students with a mean score of 3.78 and 3.85 admit having difficulties when writing in English. This suggests that, on average, these students faced challenges in English writing, emphasizing the need for potential improvements in language education and support systems. Most of the school and university students struggle with the lexical and content components of writing and info on writing issues, but university students have more aggressive perceptions of the types of issues they face and the solutions they use to solve them.

Jiving on the crucial role played by Writing

Writing is a cornerstone of education. It enables students to demonstrate their understanding of subjects, encourages critical thinking, and supports the development of analytical and research skills. Pawliczak (2015) mentioned that writing serves as a powerful tool for conveying ideas, thoughts, and information across time and distance. In a rapidly evolving world, writing endures as an invaluable and versatile tool that enriches education and powers effective communication. Writing is a medium for artistic expression. Authors, poets, and playwrights use it to create literature, while bloggers and journalists use it to share their perspectives and stories with a wider audience to communicate. According to Ponder (2015), writing transcends temporal and spatial constraints, serving as a potent tool for transmitting ideas, thoughts, and information. It serves as an indispensable pinpoint center of education, providing a platform for writers to demonstrate their grasp of subjects, nurture critical thinking abilities, and cultivate essential analytical and research skills. The ability to write effectively empowers individuals to articulate intricate concepts, share knowledge, and express their emotions with clarity and impact (Saragih et al., 2014).

According to Göçen, (2019), writing skills tend to lose their importance day by day. However, it remains an important skill people need to adopt to train students in the kinds of thought processes that will help them become good writers. Writing can take many forms, including essays, reports, letters, stories, poems, and more. It's a skill that requires a good grasp of grammar, vocabulary, and punctuation, as well as the ability to structure your content logically and engage your audience effectively. Writing serves

various purposes, such as informing, persuading, entertaining, or expressing creativity, making it a versatile and essential communication tool (Aduradola & Ojukwu, 2013). To be able to perform this using the universal language of the world will serve as a good skill anyone can achieve. Writing in English is the process of using the English language to convey thoughts, ideas, information, or stories through text. It involves organizing words, sentences, and paragraphs in a coherent and grammatically correct manner to communicate effectively with other people.

Deciphering Coherence and Cohesion through the multitude of perspectives

Poudel & Dhankuta (2018) mentioned that Academic writing is a type of formal writing that is mostly used in periodicals and colleges. The crucial characteristics of texts in academic writing are cohesion and coherence, which allude to intra-text connectivity and the idea's contextual suitability. To ensure coherence in the text, all elements of the text must work together harmoniously to create a unified, logically structured work. When everything flows smoothly, the reader can easily follow the author's train of thought, and relevance to the main topic of the essay remains consistent throughout the work. Not only does this make it easier to understand, but it also improves the overall quality of the writing by ensuring that each paragraph, sentence, and word contributes in a focused way to the overall message and argument presented in the paper essay. Coherence is defined in the early studies of text linguistics as the link that contains all kinds of grammatical and semantic relationships between the sentences that form a text (Karadeniz, 2017). Coherence in text linguistics means that sentences in a text are linked together by grammar and meaning, making it easy to understand. It's about how words and sentences relate to each other to form clear, logical text.

Coherence is the ability of our words and paragraphs to make sense when read as a whole. When we write early drafts, we are frequently more focused on getting our ideas down on paper than making sure they flow naturally so the reader can follow our reasoning. There was no coherence between the first and second halves of the movie, for example. This is when the components of anything fit together naturally or rationally. According to Vakulenko et al. (2018), coherence in a discussion concerning background knowledge depends on the discovery of semantic relationships between concepts that are introduced throughout a conversation. The coherence of a discussion depends on discovering how the concepts introduced in the conversation are connected through their meaning.

On the other hand, another crucial component of writing is cohesiveness, which requires carefully choosing terminology and grammatical constructions to link and relate ideas throughout a text. It is an essential tool for writers to create a sense of flow and logical order in their written work. Cohesion is essentially the glue that holds multiple textual components together and enables readers to follow an author's thought process with ease. Writers can construct a coherent narrative by using cohesive tools such as transitional words, pronouns, repetition, and parallel structures (Pearson, 2018). These tools help connect concepts and make the thought process easy to follow. Moreover, coherent structure aids in effectively delivering the intended message while also improving readability. To establish cohesiveness in writing, students typically used fewer synonyms and lexical sets and more repeats. This has caused students to write subpar

essays. This means that lexical coherence components must be taught in schools so that pupils may effectively employ them when writing (Kadiri et al., 2016). Lexical coherence can be demonstrated by the way related words and terms are used together, ensuring that the reader or listener can easily follow the flow of thought.

Coherence and cohesion are important because they guarantee that written discourse, such as academic theses, achieves its primary objective of clearly communicating complex ideas and arguments. It has a significant impact on the structural integrity of literary works as the likelihood of errors and misunderstandings rises when these elements are absent or employed improperly. The flow and coherence of the writing might be disrupted by sentences that lack cohesion, potentially obscuring the intended message (Liyana, 2014). Cohesion and coherence need to be present and be properly used as they link paragraphs or sections and provide the text with the structure it requires to stand alone as a coherent whole.

Research Questions

The general objective of this research is to describe and assess the writing skills of the 12th graders in English. It also aims to answer the following questions:

1. How may the demographic profile of the respondents be described in terms of:
 - 1.1. Sex
 - 1.2. Age
 - 1.3. Section
 - 1.4. Mother Tongue
2. What is the level of writing skills of students based on the survey questionnaire according to their:
 - 2.1. Cohesive Skills
 - 2.2. Coherent Skills
3. What are the problems encountered by the students in terms of English writing?

METHODOLOGY

This research study employed a quantitative research approach to systematically investigate and analyse data related to the English writing skills of Grade 12 students. Watson (2015) stated that quantitative research is a systematic method focused on investigating social phenomena using statistical or numerical data. It employs thorough reasoning, focusing on determining the best solution to a problem rather than considering all feasible arguments or options. This quantitative study makes use of survey research, which enables a choice of methodologies for participant recruitment, data collection, and instrumentation (Ponto, 2015). A total of 54 respondents from the overall population of 121 Senior High School students taking the Humanities and Social Science (HUMSS) track from a higher educational institution situated in Pampanga, Philippines, was recognized as the respondents of the study. The respondents were gathered using Taro Yamane's formula to calculate the number of respondents with the equation $54 = 121/$

(1+121 (0.10) 2). In this study, 54 identified respondents took part in the data-gathering procedure. Respondents were selected randomly, and the probability of choosing everyone from the population is the same and equal (Sharma, 2017).

This research involved a survey questionnaire answered by the participants. The researchers prepared a carefully crafted questionnaire, which is the instrument used to gather the data needed to assess and measure the cohesion and coherence skills of the senior high school students. The survey contains questions that are honestly answered by the respondents in regards with their writing skills. It is divided into five (5) subscales: Cohesion Skills, Coherence Skills, Style and Tone, Paragraph Structure, and Vocabulary and Word Choice to assess the strategies used by the learners in structuring a meaningful and purposeful text. This study employed probability sampling, specifically a random sampling selection of a sample from a given population based on the principle of randomization. In the random sampling technique, every member of the population has an equal probability of being chosen to be a respondent or a participant (Thomas, 2020). This sampling allows the research to be valid and eliminates any signs of bias because the sample is chosen randomly. Horton (2023) stated that the random sampling technique usually results in a balanced subset that has the best chance of accurately portraying the broader group as a whole. Thus, the random sampling technique is appropriate in this study as it allows the researchers to randomly and equally choose from a large population that makes up the subset that would represent the whole.

The study commenced by drafting a formal letter of consent, which was dispatched to both the school head and the strand coordinator of HUMSS 12, to ensure their active and informed involvement in the study, aligning with the established academic protocols within the school premises. Recognizing their integral role as collaborators in the study, the respondents received detailed informed consent. The primary objective of this study is to conduct a comprehensive analysis of the cohesion and coherence skills exhibited by Grade 12 students in their English writing. In pursuit of this goal, the researchers employed a survey questionnaire meticulously crafted by the researchers, designed to evaluate the students' ability in written content. In this phase, the researchers introduced the study's instrument to the participants, facilitating their engagement with the survey. Alongside this, the researchers provided essential guidance to ensure that the participants understand the instructions clearly and monitor the process to maintain its integrity.

The researchers employed a Descriptive Statistical Analysis to measure and analyze the necessary data collected from the participants. According to Mishra et al. (2019), it is a statistical method used to summarize data in a valid and meaningful way by describing the basic features. The data was collected and summarized in a way that only makes statements about the range of data from which the researchers calculated and does not go beyond the data they have. Furthermore, the researchers selected Descriptive Statistical Analysis to employ because this aids in measuring the writing skills of Grade 12 students in English in accordance with their cohesion and coherence skills by effectively simplifying the data and information collected using charts, graphs, and tables.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Demographic Profile of the Respondents

Sex

Table 1 displays the distribution of respondents' sex along with percentages. According to the findings, the majority of Grade 12 HUMSS students in a higher educational institution situated in Pampanga are female, with a frequency of 30 (55.6%), while male respondents account for a frequency of 24 (44.4%).

Age

Table 1 presents the demographic profile distribution of participants in the study, encompassing individuals within the age range of 16 to 21 years. The leading group comprises those at the age of 17, constituting 62.9% of the respondents. Subsequent age groups include 18-year-olds at 30.3%, 19-year-olds at 11.1%, 16-year-olds at 3.7%, and a lesser proportion of individuals aged 20 and 21 years, each comprising 1.9% of the total population.

Section

Table 1 shows the frequency distribution and the percentage of the HUMSS class sections of the respondents. Among these HUMSS 12-Y1-2R has the highest frequency, with 21 students, making up 33.9% of the whole. Following this is HUMSS 12-Y1-1P, comprising 17 students, representing 31.5%, and HUMSS 12-Y1-1P has a frequency of 16, comprising 29.6% of the overall student distribution. These percentages provide insight into the proportional representation of each class, offering a comprehensive view of the student composition within the academic setting.

Mother Tongue

Also, Table 1 shows an overview of the respondents' mother tongue, detailing the frequency and percentages. The data highlights that the primary mother tongue among the respondents is Tagalog, with 46 individuals, representing 85.1% of the total. Following this, Kapampangan appeared as the second most prevalent mother tongue, accounting for a frequency of 5 and a percentage of 9.3%. Additionally, the table shows the presence of English as a mother tongue, with a frequency of 5 and a percentage of 9.3%. Lastly, the mother tongue identified as Bisaya reflects the lowest frequency and percentage, with 1 respondent accounting for 1.9% of the total.

Table 1**Frequency Distribution and Percentage of the Respondents table**

<i>Demographic profile</i>		Frequency	%
Sex			
	Male	24	44.4
	Female	30	55.6
Age			
	16	2	3.7
	17	33	61.1
	18	10	18.5
	19	7	13
	20	1	1.9
	21	1	1.9
Section			
	HUMSS 12-Y1-1P	17	31.5
	HUMSS 12-Y1-1R	16	29.6
	HUMSS 12-Y1-2R	21	33.9
Mother Tongue			
	Filipino	46	85.1
	English	2	3.7
	Kapampangan	5	9.3
	Bisaya	1	1.9

Writing Skills

Senior high school students' writing skills was assessed along with five (5) subscales: The ability of Grade 12 students to write cohesively; The ability of Grade 12 students to write coherently; Style and tone proficiency in writing; Paragraph structure proficiency in writing; Vocabulary and word choice proficiency in writing.

Grade 12 students' ability to write cohesively

Table 2 exhibited that the majority of the Grade 12 HUMSS students “Disagreed” with most items in the subscale “Ability of Grade 12 students to write cohesively” with a weighted mean of 2.24 and a standard deviation of 0.88. Aguib & Bouaziz (2017) argued that students are generally weak in achieving cohesion in their writing tasks because they think correct structure and spelling are enough. There is a lack of coherence in students’ writing due to a misconception about what constitutes good writing, resulting in a lack of ability to construct a written text cohesively, with ideas structured in a scholarly way. This is congruent with the analysis of Seikmann et al. (2022), who concludes that the connections between the students’ paragraphs and ideas were lacking, hindering the overall coherence. Table 1 shows that a mean score of 2.56 and a standard deviation of 0.90 claims to “Agree” that they employ diverse strategies to ensure clear organization. However, most of the respondents are found to be unable to effectively connect ideas logically, use proper transition words or phrases, and integrate cohesive devices to produce a clear and purposeful written work. In the study of Faradhibah & Nur (2017), they found that most students find difficulties in maintaining their cohesion in the writing process because they do not know how to choose their ideas and where to put them down. The difficulties arise from uncertainty about where to incorporate specific thoughts or concepts, and without a clear grasp of how to choose and appropriately position their ideas, students find it challenging to establish a logical flow in their writing, resulting in a lack of cohesiveness in their compositions.

Grade 12 students' ability to write coherently

Based on the responses from the participants, the lack of coherent skills is apparent. Table 2 displayed the mean and standard deviation of the items under the subscale “Ability of grade 12 students to write cohesively,” revealing a weighted mean of 2.35 and a standard deviation of 0.88. This numerical representation indicates that most respondents “Disagreed” regarding their proficiency in cohesive writing. Fitriati & Yonata (2017) found that students show weakness in achieving coherent text due to a lack of optimization of cohesive devices to create interconnectedness of whole sentences. The challenge to write cohesively is further compounded by a lack of essential skills and foundational knowledge in organizing written content logically and sustaining a consistent focus on ideas or topics. Consequently, the difficulty in producing a coherent and comprehensive written work often results in misunderstandings, as highlighted by Harandi and Fatemipour (2016). Notably, the survey indicates that the respondents possess good knowledge of the importance of revisions and refining works, garnering a mean score of 2.57 and a standard deviation of 0.89. According to Lawrence (2021), revision is an integral part of any good writing process, as it helps one to gain a diverse viewpoint on their work. The respondents show awareness in their need to revise their writing hinting their attempts to resolve issues on coherence. However, if students struggle to employ various revision and writing strategies effectively, they may still face challenges in creating a coherent written piece. Hence, there is a risk of misinterpretations and perplexity arising between the author and the reader (Galea et al., 2014).

Style and tone proficiency in writing

As displayed in Table 3, respondents “Agreed” with most of the items on the subscale “Style and tone proficiency in writing,” with a weighted mean of 2.90 and a standard deviation of 0.96. In the study of Aull (2015), he concluded that each student passage demonstrated an “objective tone” and/or “formal style,” including features consistent with academic uses of features. Based on the results, the respondents “Strongly agreed” that they pay attention to the tone used in their written works. The item “I am conscious of the appropriate tone for different types of writing (e.g., formal, informal, persuasive, etc.)” gained a high mean of 3.30 and a standard deviation of 0.64 in this subscale. This implies that the students consistently demonstrated characteristics associated with the use of appropriate style and tone, thereby reflecting their proficiency. This springs from the writer’s way of expressing emotions through a range of attitudes, creating connections, and building relationships between the audience, author, subject, and text (Horkoff, 2021). Grasping and adapting the intricacies of tone and style enables students to enhance their ability to clearly state their writing’s purpose and capture the attention of people. Also, Horkoff (2015) states that when the tone and style match the content, the audience will be more engaged, building a stronger relationship with your readers.

Paragraph structure proficiency in writing

Per the results obtained from the data, the subscale "Paragraph structure proficiency in writing" has a weighted mean of 2.21 and a standard deviation of 0.96, which means that the respondents "Disagreed," with all the items listed on the said subscale. Rahman (2022) found that students suffer from poor writing skills due to the belief that paragraphs have no rules, leading to poor development and coherence. This belief can contribute to difficulties in organizing ideas, constructing sentences, applying grammar rules, and using supporting details. Essentially, if students don't follow guidelines or principles, they will struggle with constructing good paragraphs due to a lack of skill and knowledge (Arrang & Sallata, 2018). This might lead to challenges such as a lack of logical flow and misunderstanding, resulting in a clear incompetency of students in paragraph structuring. The item that receives the highest mean of 2.39 and a standard deviation of 0.93 is "I am knowledgeable of grammar rules and apply them properly when it comes to English writing." Despite having the highest mean score, it remains one of the problems that hinders the students from structuring a paragraph that is clear, concise, and purposeful. According to Mahmoud (2014), a shortage of knowledge of grammatical rules leads to a decline in achievement and failure in skill development for students. Proficiency in grammar involves understanding the various rules that govern the correct usage of language, punctuation, word choice, and sentence structure. The lack of proficiency in grammar rules will hinder one’s ability to create a well-structured and coherent paragraph.

Vocabulary and word choice proficiency in writing

Table 2 shows that the majority of respondents “Disagreed” with the items under the subscale “Vocabulary and word choice proficiency in writing,” with a weighted mean of 2.49 and a standard deviation of 1.02. The results show that students find difficulties in choosing the proper choice of words and vocabulary. According to Thuy et al. (2022), many students believed that their vocabulary was not adequate for academic writing (52.6%). Students often find trouble choosing the right and appropriate words to use in their written works due to their limited vocabulary, restricting their ability to express ideas with precision and nuance. Additionally, Table 2 shows that a mean score of 2.72 and a standard deviation of 0.97 “agreed” that they rarely use colloquial or vernacular language in their writing but still believed they lacked the necessary knowledge in vocabulary and word choice. While having the awareness that they should avoid using inappropriate words, students encounter struggles in selecting words that enhance the overall quality of their writing. As per Ashrafzadeh & Nimehchisalem (2015), almost all the students (over 97%) achieved ‘fair to poor’ vocabulary scores in their performance. Students struggle with selecting the appropriate word choice and registers based on the situation and context of their essay (Toba et al., 2019). This suggests students encountered issues not only in their vocabulary and word choice but also in applying it to their written works because while students can identify the appropriate word choice for their scholarly writing and recognize its basic features, they often do not fully understand it (Thuy et al., 2022).

Table 2

Benchmark Statements for Writing Skills	Mean	SD	Verbal Interpretation
Grade 12 students' ability to write cohesively			
1. I find it easy to connect my ideas logically in my writing.	2.19	0.88	Disagree
2. When conveying a complex idea in written English, I employ diverse strategies to ensure its clear organization.	2.56	0.90	Agree
3. I effectively use transition words and phrases to connect different parts of my writing.	2.11	0.85	Disagree
4. The relationship between sentences and paragraphs in my writing is clear and purposeful.	2.13	0.86	Disagree
5. I integrate cohesive devices, such as pronouns and repetition, to enhance the overall coherence of my compositions.	2.24	0.88	Disagree
Weighted mean	2.24	0.88	Disagree
Grade 12 students' ability to write coherently			
1. The overall organization of my written works is mostly clear and understandable.	2.33	0.84	Disagree
2. I consistently and correctly present ideas in a logical sequence, to make it easy for the readers to follow my argument.	2.25	0.93	Disagree
3. I maintain a consistent focus on the main topic or thesis throughout my writing.	2.44	0.81	Disagree
4. I constantly revise and refine my written work to enhance overall coherence and clarity.	2.57	0.89	Agree
5. My writing effectively conveys the intended meaning without confusion.	2.11	0.83	Disagree
Weighted mean	2.35	0.88	Disagree
Style and tone proficiency in writing			
1. I am conscious of the appropriate tone for different types of writing (e.g., formal, informal, persuasive, etc.).	3.30	0.64	Strongly Agree
2. My writing style is engaging and captures the reader's attention.	2.61	1.14	Agree
3. I don't have trouble adapting my writing style to suit the purpose and audience of the piece.	2.81	1.02	Agree
Weighted mean	2.90	0.96	Agree
Paragraph structure proficiency in writing			
1. Each paragraph in my writing has a clear topic sentence that introduces the main idea.	2.13	0.94	Disagree
2. I effectively use supporting details and examples to develop my paragraphs.	2.13	0.98	Disagree
3. I am knowledgeable of grammar rules and applies them properly when it comes to English writing.	2.39	0.93	Disagree
Weighted mean	2.21	0.96	Disagree
Vocabulary and word choice proficiency in writing			
1. My vocabulary is wide and precise, enhancing the clarity of my writing.	2.33	1.05	Disagree
2. I rarely use colloquial or vernacular language in my writing.	2.72	0.97	Agree
3. My choice of words always contributes to the overall impact and effectiveness of my writing.	2.38	1.01	Disagree
Weighted mean	2.49	1.02	Disagree
Grand weighted mean	2.41	0.96	Disagree

Struggles Faced by Students in the Craft of Writing

Use of Transitional Words or Phrases

Table 3 shows that a mean of 2.11 and a standard deviation of 0.85 struggle with using transitional words or phrases to connect ideas in their writing. This aligns with Sudirman & Tiasari (2015), who concluded that students struggle with logical divisions of ideas in expository essays, such as proving unity, integrating ideas, and determining correct dictions. To connect ideas, proper knowledge and application of transitional words or phrases are essential. These elements will serve as a solid bridge between thoughts, helping to establish cohesion and coherence. However, a lack of sufficient skill in its employment, such as unsuitable didactic implications, techniques, strategies, inadequate

information, misusing, and overusing, will result in the disjointed flow of ideas, leading to a diminished overall quality of written work and potentially hindering effective communication of ideas. Hama (2021) proved the same thing that students' proficiency in the use of various transitional words is lacking because they have made a variety of errors.

Paragraph structuring

Table 3 shows that a mean of 2.13 and a standard deviation of 0.94 struggle with paragraph structuring. Paragraph structuring is a crucial part of the writing process, serving organized and present ideas that enhance the readability of the work. It facilitates a unified topic or idea, allowing readers to comprehend the text more effectively. However, the data shows that the majority of students face difficulties in producing clear topic sentences in their paragraphs. Yunhadi (2016) argued that students find difficulty in paragraph writing because they lack knowledge of the structural parts and functions of a paragraph, such as topic sentences, supporting sentences, and concluding sentences, causing them to include unrelated ideas in their writing. This difficulty is concerned with the implementation of writing elements like vocabulary, grammar, and mechanics, as well as poor organization of ideas from specific to general, consistent topic discussion, and poor supporting sentences (Fauzan et al., 2022).

Use of Supporting Details or Examples

Table 3 presents the frequency distribution and the corresponding percentage of the respondents, particularly in their use of supporting details or examples. The results show that a mean of 2.13 and a standard deviation of 0.98 have difficulties using supporting details or examples in their writing. A study by Jung (2020) claims that students who write without content support are more likely to pause longer and more frequently between sentences and insert additional information. This implies that the students' struggle in integrating supporting details or examples may not only impact the clarity and depth of their written content but also consume their time and influence the overall fluency and flow of their writing process. This is in line with Wirantaka (2016), who concludes that there were problems related to coherence, cohesiveness, and effective sentences because the paragraph is not sufficiently developed through its supporting details.

Grammar

In terms of grammar, it is shown in Table 3 that a mean of 2.39 and a standard deviation of 0.93 have insufficient knowledge of the grammar rules, demonstrating an evident problem that will continue throughout the entirety of their written work. Students stated that they have limited knowledge of grammar, leading to errors like incorrect use of subject-verb agreement, tenses, pronouns, auxiliary verb, plural form, -s/-es and -ed forms (Toba & Noor, 2019). Grammar is not merely a set of rigid rules but a foundation that ensures a clear structure of written expressions. Problems in grammar significantly hinder their ability to construct a well-structured paragraph and incorporate supporting details or examples seamlessly. This correlates with the findings of Handayani & Johan

(2018), who concluded that more than 50% of students had problems in grammar that greatly influenced their writing ability.

Maintaining Consistent Focus

As shown in Table 3, most respondents struggle to maintain consistent focus in their writing, with a mean of 2.44 and a standard deviation of 0.81. In the study by Gunn (2013), he found that students often lack focus on a specific topic within a text. Maintaining topic consistency has also been observed in students from other institutions and grade levels, suggesting that students often face deficiencies in expressing their ideas coherently, making it challenging to adhere to a central theme throughout their writing. According to Toba & Noor (2019), students find difficulties in exploring and developing ideas due to concerns about whether their ideas are relevant, resulting in unknowledgeable and inconsistent ideas sometimes. This difficulty may hinder the reader's ability to follow and engage with the intended message.

Vocabulary and Word Choice

Based on the results displayed in Table 3, a mean of 2.33 and a standard deviation of 1.05 have limited vocabulary and find difficulties with word choice. Hameed & Challob (2022) found that students lack sufficient vocabulary knowledge, leading to struggle with selecting appropriate synonyms in their writing. Most students lack the necessary linguistic tools needed to clearly and precisely express their ideas. According to Tanasy & Nashruddin (2020) students were facing difficulties in transferring their thoughts, leading to incorrect use of verbs, connectors, prepositions, articles and determiners in writing. Their limited vocabulary and struggles with finding the right choice of words may result in simplistic or repetitive language that can weaken the richness of their written works, demonstrating an evident problem in the students' writing skills.

Table 3

Descriptive Statistics

<i>Struggles Faced by Students in the Craft of Writing</i>	<i>Mean</i>	<i>SD</i>	<i>Verbal Interpretation</i>
Use of Transitional Words or Phrases	2.11	0.85	Disagree
Paragraph structuring	2.13	0.94	Disagree
Use of Supporting Details or Examples	2.13	0.98	Disagree
Grammar	2.39	0.93	Disagree
Maintaining Consistent Focus	2.44	0.81	Disagree
Vocabulary and Word Choice	2.33	1.05	Disagree

Conclusions

The following are the conclusions in accordance with the summary of the results.

1. Primarily, the respondents of this study were mostly female students. In terms of age, the respondents range from ages 16–21-year-old. Besides, the study revealed that most of the respondents belonged to the HUMSS 12-Y1-2R class within a higher educational institution in Pampanga. Moreover, it was found out that main mother tongue of the respondents is Tagalog.
2. The researchers have drawn from the study that Grade 12 Humanities and Social Sciences (HUMSS) students lack proficiency in constructing a cohesive written work, indicating a relatively low level of writing skills. Despite employing diverse strategies for clear organization, the majority of students struggle to effectively connect ideas, employ proper transitions, and integrate cohesive devices in the entirety of their written work. This arises due to students' uncertainty concerning the integration of their thoughts and ideas, leading to difficulties in cultivating a coherent and logical flow in their writing, thereby indicating a deficiency in overall cohesiveness.
3. The researchers have drawn from the study that Grade 12 Humanities and Social Sciences (HUMSS) students lack proficiency in constructing a coherent written work indicating a relatively low level of writing skills. It was found that this linked to not using cohesive devices well, making it hard to create sentences that connect. Additionally, the

problem is made worse by a lack of necessary skills and basic knowledge about organizing ideas logically and staying focused on a theme. Even though the respondents

recognize the value of revisions and despite being aware, they still have trouble producing a clear and comprehensible written work.

4. Substantially, most of the students 'disagreed' with all the items under the subscale "Paragraph structure proficiency in writing". Conversely, most of the respondents 'agreed' with all the items under the subscale "Style and tone proficiency in writing".

5. The researchers found that student's encounter diverse difficulties in areas such as vocabulary and word choice, grammar, paragraph structuring, use of supporting details or examples, and use of transitional words or phrases in their writing.

6. Most Grade 12 Humanities and Social Sciences (HUMSS) students struggles to understand and effectively incorporate the diverse writing strategies to improve the overall cohesion and coherence of their works.

7. The Grade 12 Humanities and Social Sciences (HUMSS) students of a higher educational institution situated in Pampanga have insufficient knowledge and skills in terms of writing.

Recommendations

In line with the findings and conclusion of the study, the researchers arrived at the proceeding recommendations:

1. The researchers encourage teachers to analyze the writing strategies employed by the learners if it is intended to overcome actual writing problems. Teachers may organize their inventory of writing strategies used by the learners and cluster it according to their student's proficiency level and point out if there are significant differences or relationships to assess if the effectiveness of writing strategies vary.

2. In consideration of the problems that influenced learners' writing skills, the researchers suggest that teachers must guide learners who are faced with writing difficulties such as lack of confidence, lack of vocabulary, and problematic sentence construction, especially in academic writing.

3. Curriculum developers and implementers may use this study as a basis for classroom policy highlighting the significance of various written strategies in developing writing skills

particular to a writing class. This includes awareness and class-based training and exercises for learners in using written strategies.

4. Since this study was demarcated only to the Grade 12 Humanities and Social Sciences (HUMSS) students as respondents, it may be recommended that other students from other grade levels be considered as writing skills may differ among individuals.

5. Further study must be done exploring cohesion and coherence skills and how they can be taught in the class. Applicable teaching strategies, activities, and interventions must be provided to gauge both the teachability and learnability of writing strategies towards the betterment of learners' skills.

6. It is recommended that; future researchers craft a writing assessment to be answered by the respondents and evaluated by an expert in the field using a certain criterion to better challenge and assess the writing skills of the respondents.

Compliance with Ethical Standards

This research strictly adheres to the ethical standards set by the institution and the body of knowledge. All information and data coming from the respondents are solely for academic purposes only. In line also with the Data Privacy Act of 2012, the researchers strictly preserved the anonymity and confidentiality of the respondents.

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